

Stabilization of Financial Relations: Decisive Theoretical and Practical Actions

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Abstract: *The article considers the issues of theoretical and practical aspects of stabilization of financial relations. It is noted that the tendency of formation of financial resources dictates the need to find ways of development and growth of the resource component of production. The article presents some issues of the study of financial relations and financial support of innovation and investment potential, considers its key elements within the financial mechanism. It is noted that the financial mechanism as a concept is actively developing among economists, theorists, researchers, and practitioners. And this term, which has received wide publicity since the end of the 19th century, is still relevant today. The article disclosed in more detail the instruments of the financial mechanism, forms and methods of distribution, allowing for a comprehensive analysis based on the systematization of the views of economists within the framework of financial regulation, within the very terminology of "norm" and "standards", the economic mechanism and its elements. The result of the study was the conclusions regarding the features of the financial potential of enterprises, which are the result of generalization of the previously studied criteria for assessing the economic mechanism, innovation and investment potential, formation of monetary funds. The value of the presented article in practical application is the possibility of choosing the most effective approach to assessing the innovation and investment potential and strengthening the financial stability of enterprises.*

Key words: *stabilization, financial relations, economic mechanism, material and monetary resources, category, process, cost, regularity, function, self-financing, budget income, norms, financial reserves, efficiency, protection fund.*

Improvement of financial and credit systems puts forward qualitatively new demands on science, including financial science. The emphasis of theoretical research should increasingly shift to the sphere of developing recommendations on issues of financial and credit mechanisms. We are talking about a new financial policy.

Modern financial policy in the context of the New Uzbekistan, arising from the State Program of the Socio-Economic Development Strategy for 2017-2021 and a number of government documents on the modernization of the financial mechanism: Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. UP-60 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", dated July 6, 2022 No. UP-165 "On Approval of the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", dated September 26, 2019 No. UP-5837 "On Measures to Further Improve the Tax Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated June 29, 2018 No. UP-5468 "On the Concept of Improving the Tax Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan"; The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2022 No. PP-307 "On organizational measures for the implementation of the strategy of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", dated July 10, 2019 No. PP-4389 "On additional measures to improve administration" and others,

and increasing the role of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of the New Uzbekistan places high demands on sectoral economic sciences, including the science of finance. They are entrusted with the tasks of understanding the patterns of economic development in the historical process of development, theoretical understanding and systematization of the phenomena of economic life, development of practical recommendations in the field of production, distribution, exchange and consumption of vital goods, forms, methods and methods of regulating production, taking into account the interests of the state as a whole, in particular, enterprises and each employee individually. The essence of ensuring a harmonious combination of interests lies in ensuring health measures not only for the existing financial policy, but also in developing methods and techniques for conducting and organizing financial relations with counterparties, optimizing the size of relations while complying with the law. In these conditions, it is necessary to evaluate established financial relations in a new way, revise established stereotypes, and construct a new innovative economic mechanism capable of ensuring stable economic growth.

Failure to take a set of special preventive measures may lead to a tightening of financial relations. We are talking about a sharp destabilization of the economy, a collapse of public finances and a blocking of the possibility of servicing the innovatively developing economy and the national debt, which may lead to a financial collapse. However, the state is able to take preventive measures that can exclude a negative development of events.

Is it possible to take preventive measures? Unfortunately, the answer to this question cannot be only positive. It would be possible to list many achievements of economic sciences that have given the country tangible scientific results and have found wide application in practice. Such scientific works include the works of: S.S. Aliyeva, T.S. Melikov, O.O. Olimzhanov, A.V. Vakhobov, A. Kodirov, B.E. Toshmurodova, M.I. Alimardanov, R. Karlibayeva, E.F. Gadaev, O.K. Iminov, N. Zhumaev, Sh.T. Toshmatov, N.Kh. Khaidarov, H. Sobirov, K.Ya. Yakhyev, M. Sharifkhodzhaev. However, the presence of serious shortcomings in monetary circulation, the imbalance in the movement of material and monetary resources, the weak activity of the financial mechanism in stimulating innovative development and increasing production efficiency indicate the obvious backwardness of economic sciences, the weakening of their influence on the phenomena and processes occurring in the economy.

The core of economic sciences is economic theory. It is called upon to create a foundation for all other economic sciences. But, unfortunately, during the period of formation of the market economy, such a foundation of the desired level was not created. Underestimation of the role of finance in economic development, formal interpretation of cost levers (money, finance, credit, price, taxes, investments) legitimized bureaucratic methods of economic management. It is known that in the mass of interests in social reproduction, the most active are the interests of the team and workers. But it is these groups of interests that have not received deep theoretical coverage in economic theory, which could not but have a negative impact on the activity of financial and other cost categories. Representatives of economic theory have written a lot about economic trends in economic development, about the laws of economic growth, but their works do not contain a truly scientific analysis of the action of these laws, their influence on all stages of reproduction.

All the current laws and situations conditioned by the development of the economy, the law of money circulation, the law of market development and other economic laws underlie economic (including financial) relations. They act inexorably, and any violation of them entails negative consequences. For many years we overestimated the gradual transition to the market, treated economic laws carelessly, believing that everything would pass painlessly. Now it is becoming clear to many that sooner or later one has to pay for ignoring the objective force of economic laws. Unfortunately, economic theory, including financial and credit theory, did not notice these violations at the time and did not create a solid scientific foundation for both sectoral economic sciences and financial science.

But it is not only a matter of the theory of economic sciences. One cannot help but see a serious lag in the sectoral economic sciences, the task of which is to study the actions of value economic categories: money, finance, credit. The economic nature of value economic categories obliges us to a comprehensive solution to economic problems associated with the movement of value. After all, the basis of all value categories is the movement of value, cash flows. Money acts as a unifying principle of all value categories, through which they interact. It is impossible to solve the financial problem of forming the working capital of enterprises without attracting credit, but it is also impossible to ensure sufficient amounts of credit resources without attracting budget funds for this purpose. Any value category cannot act in isolation.

In other words, the absence of necessary joint efforts for many years, the self-isolation of sciences, to our great regret, have led to the fact that we have almost no comprehensive studies covering the interaction of finance, credit, and price. And is this not why serious imbalances have arisen not only in such an important area as money circulation, but also in the expanded scope of criminalization of the activities of individual financial institutions, the accumulation of doubtful debts and the growth of unprofitability of economic entities ?

This is the main idea of the proposed concept of stabilization of the financial sphere and financial relations. Undoubtedly, the time has come when it is very important to more widely develop comprehensive studies that allow us to analyze all aspects of the problem and all lines of connections of finance, credit, price, and money circulation. Accordingly, the focus on comprehensive studies will help to untie many complex knots of economic relations, reveal their patterns, formulate the main requirements and optimal quantitative ratios in commodity and financial resources. At the same time, comprehensive research should be based on an organic combination of market principles of management with a set of measures of state support for targeted institutional transformations oriented toward the most promising theoretical achievements.

It seems to us that such development of economic sciences will be one of the important measures for the practical implementation of not only specific tasks arising from the Program of the country's development strategy, but will also increase the theoretical level, quality and practical significance of scientific research in the field of finance, credit, money circulation, and the entire set of market relations.

Foreign experience shows that the development of science allows achieving the desired results in a short time. Therefore, in most developed countries, an important task of sectoral economic sciences is to strengthen the theoretical understanding of phenomena and processes occurring in financial and economic relations. But, despite this, some economic sciences largely describe the practice of work, its organizational forms and do not reveal deep connections and patterns. But in countries with a transition economy, unfortunately, not only are objective patterns in market relations not sought and revealed, but knowledge of economic laws is not fully used. In fact, not a single fundamental textbook on financial science reveals the impact of money functions on financial relations. At the same time, money is not mentioned in scientific monographs on finance, credit and taxes. Paradoxically, money underlies financial relations, and the functions of finance are in no way connected with the functions of money. Although the orientation of the financial function towards the money function is a relatively complex and difficult to implement (but at the same time the most far-sighted) option for strengthening the relationship based on the use of financial relations.

Therefore, the maturity of this impact and the effectiveness of its functioning are also of paramount importance. From this, only one conclusion suggests itself: it is necessary to strengthen the theoretical aspects of the studies of the above-mentioned categories, to reveal the patterns of their action, to show the negative consequences of violating these patterns.

For many years there has been a dispute about what finance is, what its economic nature is. Is it necessary to prove that the too protracted discussion has turned into its opposite and (instead of progressive development of financial science) pulls it back? Disputes about the essence of finance have turned into a chronic disease, weakening the development of financial science and having a negative impact on practice. Now, in the process of reform, the negative impact of this dispute is felt even more strongly.

In this regard, it should be noted that back in the early 1950s, economist V.P. Dyachenko, relying on the doctrine of social reproduction, substantiated the distribution concept of finance with distribution and control functions. The core of this concept is the so-called "stock theory", which proves that distribution with the help of finance is carried out through the formation and use of funds. An analysis of scientific literature shows that there is no substantiated criticism of this concept of finance in the economic literature, although there have been many attempts. It should also be considered that certain financial scientists proposed to consider only such relations as imperative in nature as finance, and to divide the distribution function into two: the formation of funds and the use of funds (Prof. E.A. Voznesensky). The existence of financial relations in the non-production sphere was denied (Prof. A. Lyando). The need to recognize the production function of finance was defended (Prof. A.M. Alexandrov). Recently, there has been a growing tendency to recognize the so-called reproductive function of finance (Prof. M.V. Romanovsky).

However, in today's economic conditions, it is not difficult to justify and refute the invalidity of such an "amendment" in financial theory.

It is enough to recall the functions of money, discovered by K. Marx. In the reproduction process, money takes a more active part than finance. The latter, of course, are only a part of monetary relations. And, nevertheless, K. Marx did not attribute a reproductive function to them, but named five specific functions of money, substantiating their place and role at each stage of the reproduction process.¹ The misleading idea of the reproductive function arises not because finance has some additional property, but because the reproduction stages themselves do not have clearly defined boundaries. Distribution with the help of finance begins in production itself and ends at the consumption stage.

There are five main groups of financial relations of enterprises of material production: financial relations of enterprises with the state (payments to the budget and financing from the budget), financial relations of enterprises with higher organizations, financial relations of enterprises with other enterprises and organizations (payment and receipt of fines, penalties and forfeits), financial relations within the enterprise (formation and use of all funds for a specific purpose), financial relations of enterprises with banks and other financial institutions (i.e. investment funds, venture funds, insurance companies, etc.). All five groups of the vector of development of financial relations are based on one active principle - distribution, which plays a strategically important role both at the micro and macro levels of economic development. In our opinion, the efficiency and significance of distribution are a catalyst not only for their growth and development, but also for the stability of the development of financial relations.

The issues of distribution regulation are still debatable and there is no unambiguous opinion on them. Therefore, the presence of this fact determines the relevance of both distribution and regulation of financial relations in the context of assessment in order to identify their main features. One of the key essential foundations of the distribution system is also the mechanisms for ensuring financial activity and stability of financial relations through the optimal distribution of financial resources.

¹ See: Economic Theory (Political Economy): Textbook / Edited by V.I.Vidyapin, G.P.Zhuravleva. - M.: Publishing House of the Russian Economic Academy, 2000.; State and Territorial Finances: Textbook / Edited by L.I.Sergeev. - Kaliningrad: Yantarny Skaz, 2006. - 368 p.

Formation of a financial mechanism means creation of such a system of financial relations, which would economically (and not administratively) ensure the observance of the interests of the state, enterprises and each employee individually, would facilitate the coupling of these interests with the purpose of increasing the efficiency of production and development of the social sphere. It is in distribution, made dependent on the final results of the activities of enterprises and each of its employees, that the factor of influence of the state on the enterprise, and the enterprise - on each employee, lies. Therefore, not the rejection of the distribution function of finance, but its deep study and improvement of the forms and methods of distribution should occupy a central place in financial science in close connection with the actions of other cost categories.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity" (May 2, 2019, ZRU-328) can provide a great incentive to intensify the activities of economic entities at all levels². If it clearly shows the contours of the financial mechanism, the connections and dependencies of satisfying the interests of the enterprise through the financial mechanism, the formation of various monetary funds. As for the use of funds and satisfying the individual interests of employees, there is still much to study here. The intended purpose of the enterprise's monetary funds is the final stage of distribution through the financial mechanism. Therefore, at this stage, the dependence of the remuneration of each employee on his individual contribution to solving the production tasks set before the enterprise should be strengthened. This means that if the enterprise received additional income and increased its own funds due to improved product quality, then remuneration for labor should be made dependent on the individual indicator of each employee's contribution to this overall success of the enterprise. Unfortunately, we often forget about this and reward employees simply for good work, although it may not have affected the final financial results.

It is possible to double the quantity of quality products without ensuring the optimal amount of financial resources. Therefore, finances of the production sphere need deep economic research. Some economists before the transition period (Prof. A.Lyando) did not recognize the existence of separate finances of the non-production sphere at all, considering them only a component of the state budget. Apparently, this was due to the share of budget funds directed to the production sphere (up to 65% of the total budget expenditure). But today the picture has changed, no more than 30% of budget funds are directed to economic development. So, until the mid-80s of the twentieth century, they were mainly supported by budget funds. Beginning from the 90s of the twentieth century and up to the present, they are supported only by enterprises. Therefore, the cutting edge of scientific research until the end of the 80s of the twentieth century was directed mainly at the finances of material production and the state budget. This was perceived as an effective approach to distribution. The finances of education, health care, enlightenment, science, culture and other budgetary organizations have not been subjected to deep scientific research and analysis.

However, it is worth noting that the effectiveness of distribution has been and is an indicator of the financial potential of recipients of budget funds (if other sources are not provided), which is not always able to reflect the direct dependence of recipients of budget funds on the budget's capabilities. Since budget expenditure includes, in the broad sense of the word, not only a set of certain separately established resource expenditures taking into account the needs of recipients of budget funds, but does not take into account the nature of the relationship between distribution and use (result), between the conditions and the nature of the budget's capabilities or budget potential.

² This Law was adopted in 2000 (May 25), although before that, that is, before January 20, 2001, such a law was the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Enterprises".

Thus, according to this direction, budgetary potential is not only the available financial resources to satisfy the recipients of budgetary funds, but also a system of optimally interconnected individual financial relations.

Now, first of all, it is necessary to resolve the issue of successive stages, forms and methods of transferring non-production organizations to full self-sufficiency and self-financing. It is no coincidence that since January 2020, 10 universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been transferred to self-financing as an experiment. Recognizing the importance of developing and scientifically substantiating intermediate forms of transition from budget financing to partial or full self-financing is becoming especially relevant. Now it is equally important to determine the factors of outstripping the importance of financial science in the context of reforming budget financing in order to link it with the final results of the activities of recipients of budget funds. This is evidenced by the experience of financing some medical institutions and research institutes depending on the number of cured patients. The distribution of the so-called "budget income" and the formation of the salary of each employee depending on the qualifications and position and category held are originally organized in these institutes. Studying these examples, improving them and giving them the correct theoretical justification is one of the most important tasks of financial science. The issue is changing the very nature of gratuitous financing, giving it a productive character, making it dependent on final results. We are also obliged to do this by rejecting budget financing and the normative method of financial support. Estimates have always limited the economic independence of budget organizations, turning their managers into passive managers, thinking only about spending budget allocations at any cost.

But replacing budget financing with standard financing will not have much effect unless a system of material incentives for saving funds against the standard is developed. However, incentives should not be provided for any savings, but only for the actual gain obtained when using budget funds. For example, it is impossible to consider funds remaining with the organization as real savings as a result of the fact that the planned activities were not carried out for one reason or another.

In addition, an objective prerequisite for eliminating unresolved problems in the context of financial science is the creation of the theory of financial regulation in the structure of the category of finance. In addition, an objective prerequisite for the emergence of the category of financial regulation in the composition of financial science was the need for recipients of budgetary funds - institutions in legal protection of their results in the use of budgetary funds.

Norms and standards are the most popular words of modernization and restructuring. What do we know about them from financial science? Unfortunately, very little. There is even confusion in the terminology itself and, in particular, we do not have a unified opinion on the differences between a norm and a standard. In some cases, a norm is called a standard, and in others, a standard is included among the norms. It seems to us that a norm should be considered an established amount of material or labor resources calculated for a particular unit. It is probably more correct to understand a standard as a legislatively or administratively established quantitative expression of material values or money calculated for a unit according to current standards.

In our opinion, one of the priority tasks within the category of "norm" or "standard" is the issue of forming the financial potential of recipients of budgetary funds, i.e. that part of the funds necessary for forming indicators that can be of value for the production, management or other process of recipients of budgetary funds at present and in the future. This transformation, in our opinion, is a process of standardization of financial resources and knowledge of financial science in a material form, during which it will be separated from the carrier - the norm and transition to an independent form of existence under certain conditions as the category of "standardization". The latter is a synthesis of several indicators of a financial resource nature, which together will provide recipients of budgetary funds with the opportunity to create resources sufficient to ensure the stability of development.

The creation of scientifically substantiated standards for payments to the state budget, standards for profit distribution, standards for the formation of economic incentives, standards for working capital are difficult tasks that enterprises and financial bodies have to solve. But no one has yet said what a standard is, what its economic nature is, what objective limits determine its upper and lower boundaries, what economic laws operate here. Meanwhile, financial standards and norms ultimately predetermine the financial condition of enterprises, proportions in the national economy, and the priority of individual industries. They must ensure a balance in the movement of material resources and funds, prevent distortions in the economy, create harmony in the distribution of GDP and GNI, while strictly observing the principles of social justice.

It seems that there is a need to create a domestic theory of the formation of norms and standards, which would provide certain theoretical guidelines for practice. It is important to work out the economic mechanism very well, to create a coherent system of financial relations in material production and in the non-production sphere, but the success of the matter will depend on the level of norms and standards. Errors in them can negate the advantages of the norms of financial relations, give rise to new disproportions in the economy. It is necessary not only to reveal the objective patterns of the formation of financial norms and standards, but also to show the entire process of their aggregation at different levels of financial regulation, to reveal the influence of norms on the distribution process.

In other words, a very important problem in the current conditions is the problem of differentiation and unification of norms as a whole or their individual elements. From here we see an interesting detail: there are, as it were, two dimensions that can designate the efficiency of enterprises. In fairness, it should be noted that there are two scientific views on this matter. Supporters of unified norms believe that only a unified norm is an active driving force, since a unified norm will force those lagging behind to intensify their activities and catch up with competitors. Supporters of the second point of view, i.e. differentiation of norms, put forward an antithesis based only on the individual characteristics of each enterprise.

From here we see one curious detail: there are, as it were, two dimensions of business activity of enterprises. Each of them strives to ensure the effective work of enterprises. In our opinion, the truth, as is often the case in controversial issues, is somewhere in the middle. Of course, we must objectively strive for a single standard, especially in cases where the differences between enterprises are purely subjective, i.e. entirely dependent on the direction of their activities and the effectiveness of their work. But there are also other segments that characterize the features of objective origin (differences in climatic conditions), which strengthen or weaken the effectiveness of the enterprise. One cannot ignore the level of technical equipment and technological features, as well as the innovative orientation of enterprises.

An important financial problem is the creation of financial reserves, capable of ensuring innovative development in sufficient volume. Unfortunately, this problem is also poorly developed by financial science, and, meanwhile, a large number of all kinds of financial difficulties prevent an enterprise from activating its activities or working successfully. Consequently, financial difficulties arise due to the lack of financial reserves. Reserves and proportionality in the economy are not adequate concepts, but only related concepts. No matter how much we talk about stability in the economy, we are not free from all kinds of accidents and unforeseen circumstances. The absence or insufficiency of financial reserves often puts at risk not only individual innovatively developing enterprises, but also entire sectors (spheres) of the economy.

In other words: what should these financial reserves be, how and where should they be formed, at the expense of what financial source and in what economic limits or sizes? Without going into a detailed theoretical analysis of these concepts, we will only note that the real volume of financial resources is inertial and can be quite stable or very dynamic. Economists have something to work on here. Obviously, the most correct line should be the centralization of reserve funds.

According to the simplest and most logically explainable approach, in our opinion, it is very important to study the issue of the quantitative relationship between natural (material) and financial reserves. Experience shows that financial reserves do not achieve their goal if material reserves do not come into effect simultaneously with them. But financial reserves, cleared of the inflationary influence, can be smaller in size than the total value of material reserves, since monetary reserves, as a universal equivalent, can come into effect in any case, while material reserves can prevent the arising disproportion if they are based on a specific type of materials. Consequently, the financial reserves of an enterprise are its ability to function and develop, maintain the balance of its assets and liabilities in a changing internal and external environment, guaranteeing its constant solvency and innovative and investment attractiveness within the limits of the acceptable level of risk.

Financial science should not ignore the social and environmental problems of the country, since the protection of society from environmental consequences and the social protection of the poor have begun to acquire a global character. Naturally, their financial support is acquiring exceptional importance. In particular, we annually spend billions of sums on environmental activities. But, probably, no financier can say today where, how and how effectively these funds are spent. If this problem becomes more urgent or acute, then it will be necessary to urgently develop a comprehensive system of struggle for the preservation of natural conditions of human life. Hence, the obvious conclusion is that a system of formation of environmental protection funds should be created, starting from the enterprise and ending with ministries and the state budget. The fact is that environmental activities should be carried out on different scales and at different levels with the allocation of the necessary resources to eliminate the inflationary impact. They can be carried out on a national scale, in particular, within each enterprise individually. Stable sources of financial resources are needed for these purposes and at different levels of implementation of law-like activities. In our opinion, a regulatory and legal procedure for the formation and use of each fund should be established, taking into account the scope of their activities. But, despite this, the duty of financial science is to make its contribution to solving this problem.

As we know, the terms “mechanism”, “financial mechanism”, “tax mechanism”, etc. are often mentioned in adopted legislative acts on the one hand, and in economic literature on the other.³ Among them, the following are singled out: “budget mechanism”, “credit mechanism”, “insurance mechanism”, “innovation-investment mechanism”, “social security mechanism”, etc.

At the same time, there is no comprehensive approach that would provide for the systematization of the entire arsenal of elements of the economic mechanism. A mechanism for assessing the effectiveness of their use has not been developed. At the same time, the problem of financial support for entities should be considered as a condition for the development of an economic entity and ensuring the stability of development, which determines the relevance of the terms under consideration.

The formation of a mechanism for financial support for functioning and development involves determining the essential characteristics of this mechanism.

The concept of mechanism came to economics from technology, as the need arose to describe social and production processes in their interaction. In this analogy, the possibility of obtaining a positive effect is important.

Prototypes of the simplest mechanisms, borrowed from mechanics (lever, inclined plane, etc.), in economics formed a group of so-called tools that are part of the mechanism.

And the economic mechanism has a rather complex structure.

³ Abalkin L.I. Selected Works. In 4 volumes. Vol. II . On the Way to Reform. Economic Mechanism ... of Society. New Type of Economic Thinking. Perestroika: Paths and Problems. - M., 2000.

The term “mechanism” has taken hold, and modern economic research is replete with such concepts as “organizational -economic mechanism”, “financial mechanism”, “management mechanism”, “economic mechanism”, “mechanism of socio-economic development”, etc.⁴

A mechanism is understood as a set of states of a system or the main driving force of development.

In this case, the question arises: what is a "financial mechanism" - is it a process or a resource? In answering this question, I would like to give a definition. A financial mechanism is an integral part of the economic mechanism, expressed in the totality of financial resources and methods of their connection with the help of its elements - management, planning and stimulation. A distinctive feature of the proposed definition is the presence of a process and the inseparable connection and subordination of the elements of the mechanism to the process. That is, all elements are built as a controlled resource of a specific process.

If we consider the mechanism of financial support or financial provision as a single system, then the elements of the financial mechanism can include:

- management of financial relations (including investment, lending, insurance, etc.);
- financial planning (these are the levers – profit, price, taxes, regulation, analysis, control, etc.);
- stimulation (i.e. the process of financial support, benefits, incentives, etc.).

All of them are presented within the framework of the financial mechanism. Because they are components of the financial mechanism. It is thanks to the financial mechanism and its operational regulation that the principles of self-sufficiency and self-financing are ensured.

In this regard, it seems to us that one of the most promising tasks of improving such components of the financial mechanism is the development of such financial relationships that would stimulate high quality of innovative products. It is necessary to develop a new order of financially influencing segments, in which enterprises would ensure their synergetic effect. Such an order would transform the financial regulation mechanism into a serious form of stimulation and support for innovatively developing enterprises. The development of theoretical foundations and principles of such stimulation, regulation and operational management of financial resources would serve as one of the tasks of financial science.

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